

APPLICATION OF LOCAL INTERPOLATION CUBIC SPLINE MODEL BUILT IN UNEQUAL INTERVALS

¹Qobilov Sirojiddin Sherqulovich

²Muminov Elyor Normurodovich

¹Teacher of the Department of "Artificial Intelligence" at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi

qobilov.sirojiddin92@gmail.com

²Teacher of the Department of "Artificial Intelligence" at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi

emuminov864@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15573311>

The processes of interpolation of biomedical signals obtained as a result of experimental studies are carried out using the local cubic spline model proposed in this work. The obtained results show that cubic spline models give good results in digital signal processing, which ensures that specialists make the right decision (diagnosis) as a result of digital signal processing in a certain field (in the field of medicine). The initial values of the ECG signal were digitally processed for the study. The obtained results are graphically displayed and the error results are evaluated [1,2]. The closeness of the reconstructed signal values to the original signal amplitudes and the very low error ensure the model's performance. In addition, accuracy is very important in the field of medicine. In medicine, accuracy plays an important role in processes such as determining the current condition of a patient brought to the hospital in critical condition, determining the type of disease, and determining the degree of the disease [3,5]. Increasing the degree of convergence of the models considered in this work does not depend on increasing the order of the system of equations.

1. Description of the mathematical model.

Local interpolation cubic spline functions are a high-precision mathematical tool for interpolating values given in tabular form. It is for this reason that these models are considered very important in solving practical problems. In this work, we give an overview of the spline model that gives good results in digital signal processing [4].

$$S_3(f, x) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \varphi_k(t) f(x_{i+k-2})$$

here:

$$\varphi_1(t) = -\frac{1}{4}t(1 - 3t + 2t^2); \quad \varphi_2(t) = \frac{1}{4}(4 - 3t - 7t^2 + 6t^3);$$

$$\varphi_3(t) = \frac{1}{4}t(5 + 5t - 6t^2); \quad \varphi_4(t) = -\frac{1}{4}t(1 + t - 2t^2);$$

$$t = (x - x_i)/h, \quad h = x_{i+1} - x_i, \quad x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}], \quad t \in [0, 1]$$

The theorem on the fulfillment of the interpolation conditions of the considered local interpolation cubic spline is proved in this work.

2. Digital processing of signals based on the algorithm considered in this work.

In the next step, we considered the reconstruction of the ECG signal given in Table 1 through the local interpolation cubic spline models proposed above. Based on the above sequence, a local interpolation cubic spline construction program was developed in the Python software environment and used in signal processing (Figure 1).

ECG signal values obtained by experimental measurements. Table 1.

No	Time, seconds	Amplitude	No	Time, seconds	Amplitude
1.	1	-0,060	11.	11	-0,080
2.	2	-0,065	12.	12	-0,095
3.	3	-0,060	13.	13	-0,080
4.	4	-0,075	14.	14	-0,095
5.	5	-0,065	15.	15	-0,085
6.	6	-0,070	16.	16	-0,090
7.	7	-0,070	17.	17	-0,090
8.	8	-0,090	18.	18	-0,100
9.	9	-0,080	19.	19	-0,085
10.	10	-0,095	20.	20	-0,105

A graphical representation of the above table values is given below

ECG signal recovery results. Figure 1.

The results before the study are presented in graph 1. In the course of research, our proposed spline model has been shown to be effective in digital processing of experimentally obtained signals. It is not difficult for us to see that the actual signal values in graph 1 and the values recovered by the model are not significantly different from each other, and the specified error fully satisfies the conditions. This shows us the effectiveness of the model.

References:

Используемая литература:

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Bakhromov S. A., Eshkuvatov Z. K. Error estimates for one local interpolation cubic spline with the maximum approximation order of $O(h^3)$ for $W_1[a, b]$ classes. AIP Conference Proceedings 2484 030009 (2023). doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0110417>.
2. Bakhromov S.A. Digital Processing of Signals Ryabenky Cubic Spline Model. AIP Conference Proceedings 2781 020015 (2023). doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0145980>.
3. Bahramov S.A., Jovliev S. Bicubic Splines in Problems of Modeling of Multidimensional Signal. "International journal of "the korea institute of maritime information & communication sciences". Vol.9, No.4, August 2011, p.420-423.
4. Исраилов М.И., Эшдавлатов Б. Уточнение остаточного члена одного интерполяционного сплайна. // Вопр. вычис. и прик. математики, - Ташкент: РИСО АН Узбекистана, 1986, вып. 80, С. 10-26.
5. Рябенький В.С., Филлипов А.Ф. Об устойчивости разностных уравнений. - М.: Гостехиздат. 1956, - 171 с.
6. Соболев С.Л. Введение в теорию кубатурных формул. -М.: Наука. 1974. 808 с.
7. Yusupov I, Nurmurodov J, Ibragimov S, Gofurjonov M, Qobilov S. "Calculation of Spectral Coefficients of Signals on the Basis of Haar by the Method of Machine Learning", 14th International Conference, IHCI 2022, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, October 20–22, 2022, pp 547–558. <https://link.springer.com/conference/ihci>
8. Zavyalov Yu.S., Kvasov B.I., Miroshnichenko V.L. 2008. Methods of spline functions. М.: Nauka, 1980, - 352 p.